

What is a PID?

A persistent identifier (PID) is a long-lasting digital reference to, e.g., a digital object, a person | author | contributor, a webpage, or an organization.

What does a PID do?

PIDs ensure the findability and interoperability of a digital resource (as in the [FAIR Principles](#)).

In contrast to a URL that can break or rot, a PID will always point to the right object, even when the location changes.

PIDs also certify the identity of the digital object, contributor, or organization.

What is a PID for?

1. Publishing
2. Citing
3. Archiving

Examples

[DOI](#) - Digital Object Identifier

[ARK](#) - Archival Research Key

[ORCID](#) - Open Researcher and Contributor Identifier

[Permalink](#) - Permanent Link

[HDL](#) - Handle

National PID Services

[ORCID Austria](#)

[DOI Service Austria \(TU Wien\)](#)

Adding a PID to your object helps make it EOSC ready!

